

Zhu Xi's Four Books 朱熹四書

also known as “The Collected Commentaries of the Chapters and Verses of the Four Books (四書章句集注)”

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Entry tags: Confucian (rujia 儒家) Traditions, Neo-Confucian Traditions, Religious Group, Text, Neo-Confucian text, Chinese Religion

The Four Books, namely the Great Learning (Da xue 大學), the Doctrine of the Mean (Zhong yong 中庸), the Analects (Lun yu 論語), and the Mencius (Meng zi 孟子), is a compendium of essential Confucian readings compiled, edited, annotated, and systematically interpreted by Zhu Xi 朱熹 (1130-1200 CE), the eminent Southern Song scholar and chief architect of Neo-Confucianism. It is recognized as the most fundamental canon of Neo-Confucianism and marks the climax of this intellectual movement that aims to “reexamine, rediscover, reinterpret, redefine, revitalize and reinforce” the Confucian heritage. (James T.C. Liu, 1973, p.483). About one century after Zhu Xi’s death, when the Mongolian Yuan emperor Renzong (r.1311-1320 CE) issued a decree to reintroduce the imperial examination (keju kaoshi 科舉考試) system for government recruitment in 1313 CE, he assigned Zhu Xi’s edition of the Four Books, Sishu zhangju jizhu 四書章句集注 (The Collected Commentaries of the Chapters and Verses of the Four Books, below SSZJJZ), as the basic curriculum of the imperial examination. As a result, SSZJJZ became the base of state orthodoxy and remained so for the following six hundred years till the imperial examination system was terminated in 1919. In this sense, there is no other Chinese classic that has had a greater influence on Chinese thought and life than Zhu Xi’s Four Books. Among the Four Books, the Analects and Mencius had circulated separately before the twelfth century. The other two “books” are chapters selected by Zhu Xi from the Book of Rites (Liji, 禮記), one of the Five Classics (wujing 五經). But all of the four texts have seen some extent of “ascendancy” as they became part of the Four Books. The Analects, which collects Confucius’ own words and his disciples’ remarks about the Master, had always been considered essential in rudimentary education but never made it into the Classics. (Some scholars believe the “Seven Classics” in the Eastern Han includes the Analects, but others doubt whether the phrase even refers to Confucian canons as it may refer to a group of Daoist or Buddhist scripts.) Mencius used to be merely one of the pre-Qin “masters’ books” (zishu 子書) but gradually gained more attention from the mid-Tang and onward. Leading Confucian scholars of previous generations had already noticed the hermeneutic potentials in these four groups of texts— especially the Mencius and the Doctrine of the Mean— in purifying and revitalizing the Confucian heritage, but it was in Zhu Xi’s hands that they were first combined together, prioritized in the Confucian teaching, given a systematic and coherent interpretation, and became the Four Books— a new Confucian canon and the pivot of the renewed tradition that would surpass the Five Classics to constitute the foundation of state orthodoxy. Before the Tang, the curriculum in the Imperial Academy (taixue 太學) was based on the Five Classics (wujing 五經): The Book of Poetry (Shi 詩), The Book of Documents (Shu 書), The Book of Rites, The Book of Music (Yue 樂), Spring and Autumn Annals (Chun qiu 春秋). A few other texts, such as The Analects, The Classic of Filial Piety (Xiao jing 孝經), and Er-ya (“The Literary Expositor” 爾雅) were used as auxiliary books especially for elementary education. The education at this time aimed at cultivating students’ (most of them aristocratic) Six Arts (liuyi 六藝): ceremonies (li 禮), music (yue 樂), archery (she 射), carriage-driving (yu 御), writing (shu 書), mathematics (shu 數). The pre-Tang tradition’s emphasis on the value of institution, ritual, and cultural conventions is also seen in its promotion of the parallel of “Duke of Zhou and Confucius”. This model assigns the same supreme status as Confucius to the Duke of Zhou, one of the de facto rulers in early Zhou dynasty and a seminal figure in establishing the political and cultural institutions that would impact Chinese civilization for thousands of years to come. Almost all the aforementioned characteristics of pre-Tang Confucian tradition were transformed during and after the

Song. Individuals' moral cultivation replaced the establishment of social and cultural institutions to become the most valued as the cultural synthesis had collapsed. The greatest Confucian enterprise changed from building an "external kingdom" (waiwang 外王) to attaining "inner sagehood" (neisheng 內聖). The ultimate cultural heroes, accordingly, had also changed from the parallel of "the Duke of Zhou and Confucius" to that of "Confucius and Mencius," the lesser sage (yasheng 亞聖) who brought about the discussions about the Four Cardinal Virtues/Beginnings (siduan 四端) that he believed were innate to humans and thus sparked off a long debate over human nature in Chinese history. But the most noticeable transformation from the Han-Tang Confucian doctrine to its renewed model in and after the Song till the rise of the Evidential Studies (kaoju xue 考據學) in the eighteenth century is the formulation of the idea of li 理 (Principle/ Pattern/ Coherence/ Moral Law) — where the term li xue 理學 (the Learning of Principle, or, Neo-Confucianism) comes from — and the full-blown development of Neo-Confucian hermeneutics anchored to this idea. Among all the Song dynasty Neo-Confucian philosophers Zhu Xi alone emphasizes the autonomy of knowledge and the importance of book learning to the attainment of li (or dao, the Way 道), Zhu Xi with his study of the Four Books provides a systematic methodology about it, which is precisely the area wherein lies one of his monumental contributions to the Neo-Confucian learning (Yu, 2016). The notion of li was first raised to the metaphysical level and given an ontological sense by the Cheng brothers in the eleventh century. It's defined as the substance of nature and the fundamental moving cause of myriad things. The Cheng brothers also developed the Neo-Confucian epistemology centered around the question of how we, as subjective individuals with limited cognitive faculties, could study the Principle to the utmost (qiong li 窮理) and bring our innate moral nature to its fulfillment (jin xing 盡性). Zhu Xi inherited the Cheng brothers' learning of li and further enhanced its metaphysical profundity by incorporating it with other Northern Song Confucian thinkers' cosmological studies. He also made the Neo-Confucian interpretations of li more tenable in their competition against the increasingly popular Chan School of Buddhism, the teaching of which is characterized by vacuity and its disbelief of the existence of a concrete, good and eternal entity. Li as an ontological concept is interchangeable in various contexts with a few other Confucian notions including dao (the Way 道), taiji (the Supreme Ultimate 太極), xing (Nature of man and things 性), xin (mind-heart 心, here refers to the Moral Mind-heart daoxin 道心 rather than its contaminated version, the fallible renxin 人心). Zhu Xi articulates that li is identical to dao and taiji; and it is called (human) Nature in relation to the mind-heart and Principle in relation to events and things (zai xin huanzuo xing, zai shi huanzuo li. 在心喚做性, 在事喚做理). Some scholars have found li comparable to the Aristotelian notion of form in the field of nature and to the Platonic idea of goodness in the field of moral value (Chang, 1956, pp.255-56), whereas others caution against such comparison as the usual Western polarities do not apply in Chinese philosophy (Chan, 1963, p.641). The Neo-Confucianists claim that this li does not exist for itself, thus the celebrated dictum of li yi fen shu (the Principle is one but the manifestations are many. 理一分殊). With Zhu Xi, each thing (wu wu 物物) and each person (ren ren 人人) in this phenomenal world is endowed with one/the same li or one/the same taiji. He often uses the metaphor of moon and its reflections in rivers and lakes to explain why the one li does not split up into parts while being within infinite particularities. As many have noted, this analogy is borrowed, though indirectly, from the Buddhist Huayan School's doctrine of one and many. But the real crux of the matter here is how the myriad manifestations of li— this eternal and highest goodness— are involved with conflicts, imbalance, and all kinds of deviation from the Mean (zhong yong 中庸) when it leaves the state of tranquility (that is, wei fa 未發, before it becomes active) and enters the state of differentiation as activity takes place (yi fa 已發), and how this problem of evil or badness could be solved. To respond to such a query that is perennial and universal to almost all religions and traditions of thought, the Neo-Confucians introduced the notion of qizhi zhi xing (physical nature 氣質之性. Relevant terms include qi or qi bing, material force/ material endowment 氣/氣稟). This notion was first brought into discussion by Zhu Xi's eleventh century predecessors (primarily Zhang Zai 張載 and Chengyi 程頤) then got fully elaborated in Zhu's system. According to Zhu Xi, it is not sufficient to simply blame the rising of badness on an individual's wrong choice— as Mencius does; nor is it proper to be ascribed to feelings (qing 情) — as the Tang Confucians do, because he believes qing buds from its roots of moral nature. The propensity to deviate from the Mean is actually attendant in each individual's endowment of physical nature. This does not mean however the physical nature as such is evil itself. It means that within the physical nature there is the occasion for

badness. And how to use this occasion, Zhu Xi claims, depends on man. This is why the Four Books is assigned such an essential and fundamental role in Zhu Xi's entire teaching. He believes that reading keeps one's mind from indulging in empty speculations and keeps it in a desirable state of jing (serious, attentive, alert 敬). It's only with this attitude of jing that one can prevent their nature from lapsing into laxity, avoid being controlled by the damaging material force, be able to preserve (cun 存) and cultivate (yang 養) their moral mind, and finally achieve sagehood and attain the Way. Therefore, book knowledge always precedes any practice or action in the systematic methodology Zhu Xi designed to achieve the above goals— not necessarily in the sense of importance but in the sense of order. All of these hermeneutic and methodological changes of Confucianism were institutionalized in the aforementioned 1313 decree. Such a model transformation from the Han-Tang Confucianism to the (post-) Song Neo-Confucianism, as stated in earlier passages, was not initiated by Zhu Xi. The learning of the eleventh century dao xue (the Learning of the Way 道學) scholars had laid the foundation for Zhu Xi's creative and comprehensive work. But as the chief architect of Neo-Confucianism and especially the founder of "study of the Four Books" (sishu xue 四書學), Zhu Xi is reckoned by many as the most crucial thinker in the intellectual lineage that consummated this transformation (Qian, 1982, vol.4, pp.180-81), or what Thomas S. Kunn would call it— a "paradigm shift" (Chen, 2006, p.2).

Date Range: 1177 CE - 1912 CE

Region: Southern Song (1127-1279 CE)

Region tags: China, Song China

Approximate area of the Southern Song.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: - Zhu, Xi 朱熹. Sishu zhangju jizhu 四書章句集注. Series of Xinbian zhuzi jicheng 新編諸子集成. 第一輯 (Beijing: Zhonghua shuju, 1983)
- Source 2: Chan, Wing-tsit. Selected passages in A Source Book in Chinese Philosophy (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1963).
- Source 3: Gardner, Daniel K. "Preface to the Greater Learning in Chapters and Verses" in Chu Hsi and The Ta-hsueh: Neo-Confucian Reflections on the Confucian Canon (Leiden: Brill, 1986)

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/liji/da-xue>; <https://ctext.org/liji/zhong-yong>; <https://ctext.org/analects>; <https://ctext.org/mengzi>
- Source 1 Description: Full English translation of the original texts of the Four Books, rendered by James Legge.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/si-shu-zhang-ju-ji-zhu>

– Source 1 Description: - Description: Full text of the Sishu zhangju jizhu. The content includes the original texts of the Four Books, glossaries and comments on each chapter and verse by Zhu Xi and earlier Neo-Confucian scholars. Most of the early comments Zhu Xi selected and edited are from the Cheng brothers (Cheng Hao 程顥, Cheng Yi 程頤) of the eleventh century and their disciples.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Impressed

Tool for making the impression(s)

– Other [specify]: Printed with woodblocks

Notes: 26 juan (volumes) in total.

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Notes: With brush.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Specify type of paper

– Specify: The production of this text was not restricted to any specific type of paper.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: The production of this text did not entail material modification.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: No

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: There was no financial support from the central or local government when Zhu Xi worked on SSZJJZ as a private project in the late 12th century. In fact, SSZJJZ, together with Zhu Xi's other scholarship and his entire teaching, was condemned as false learning (wei xue 偽學) and banned by the Southern Song central government during the Qingyuan reign (qingyuan dangjin 慶元黨禁), ensuring Zhu Xi and his patron's failure in the contemporaneous political struggle. The proscription was lifted a few years later. The 1313 decree issued by the Yuan court recognized SSZJJZ as the primary Neo-Confucian canon and the basic curriculum for national civil service examination, making it one of the most printed and profitable texts for the publishing industry in late imperial China. The government support also helped the dissemination of the text. The Ming court, for example, funded the compilation of The Encyclopedia of the Four Books and the Five Classics (Sishu wujing daquan 四書五經大全) in 1415 CE, which was distributed to the national university and all schools on the prefecture and county levels.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Notes: Despite being more or less an underdog in his own time and having his works banned by the court during the Qingyuan reign (1195–1200) of the Southern Song, Zhu Xi and his learning, precisely his study of the Four Books, reached its turning point in 1313 CE when Renzong (r. 1311–1320 CE) of the Yuan dynasty issued the historical decree to reintroduce the imperial examination system for official recruitment and, for the first time, adopted Zhu Xi's edition and interpretations of the Four Books as the basis for the imperial examination. This new tradition was carried through the following six hundred years till the termination of the imperial examination system in 1919 CE. The 1313 decree marks the inauguration of the dominance of Neo-Confucianism's Cheng-Zhu school in its shaping of the literati's education, career, and personal life in late imperial China.

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: The official schools (guanxue 官學), especially the National University (Taixue 太學, or Guozijian 國子監, or both, depending on which dynasty it refers to), have the authority for interpretation.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

– Yes

Notes: Many scholars had different or even heretical opinions from the official interpretation of Zhu Xi's SSZJJZ or even SSZJJZ itself. The Qing classicist scholar Mao Qiling 毛奇齡 (1623- 1716 CE), for example, is known for his vehement criticism of Zhu Xi and the general Song exegetical tradition (Songxue 宋學) that Zhu represents. In his *Correcting the Four Books* (Sishu gaicuo 四書改錯, compiled by Mao's disciples), Mao famously claims that "there is not one single thing that is not wrong in Zhu's Four Books." The mistakes and inaccuracies Mao identified in SSZJJZ add up to 451 and the covered categories range from institutional history, geography, sacrificial rituals to punctuation and copy errors.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

– No

Notes: Scholars could have their own opinions expressed in private works or taught at private academies. But the examiners who were authorized to grade the examination papers and decide who can obtain degrees in the civil examination were from the official institutions and officially sanctioned.

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

– No

Notes: There was no such a canon called the Four Books before Zhu Xi first compiled them together in the late twelfth century; and SSZJJZ soon became the orthodox curriculum after the 1313 decree was issued. Therefore, despite the existence of disagreements in scholars' private works, it's hard to say there were ever "common" disagreements about SSZJJZ in imperial China.

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: Scholars/ teachers in the official schools and National Universities are trained to teach the Four Books and its doctrines. These scholars are also the products of the Four Books education themselves as almost all of them had taken the civil examinations and many were jinshi degree holders.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– Yes

Notes: They were all males.

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– No

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– Yes

Notes: They were all Chinese speakers. They might speak different dialects in daily life, but all of them used classic Chinese as a written language and for formal communications.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Notes: At his own time, Zhu Xi's entire teaching was designed to center around the Four Books. According to various historical records, students who had studied with Zhu Xi in this way or that amounted to a few hundreds (the number ranges from 133 to 488, according to Chan, 1988, p.454). Since the Four Books was assigned to be the basic curriculum for imperial examination in Yuan, Ming and Qing, the text was studied by almost all Chinese males (and some females from prestigious families) who aimed to take the imperial exam, and by those who were simply willing to receive (and able to afford) some basic Confucian education. Although the precise total number of these learners is hard to identify, we do have the numbers of jinshi 進士 degree (the highest degree in regular imperial

civil examination) holders from the Yuan, Ming, and Qing. In Yuan, there were over one thousand jinshi; in Ming and Qing, that number exceeded fifty thousand in total.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

— No

Notes: Not on a routine basis. Neo-Confucianism in the mid and late twelfth century presents a broad spectrum of various attempts and attainments that aim for the renewal of Confucianism. Among them, Zhu Xi and his followers stand out as a very vocal and polemic voice in combating against teachings that the master personally disagrees with. If there is any deliberate intention for Zhu Xi to recruit students and amplify his impact, it is primarily demonstrated in his intellectual criticism of other schools' learning rather than developing practical strategies to promote membership or reach out to converts for their school. In public debates and in private letter exchanges, many of which in fact were never intended to be private as Zhu Xi would encourage anyone involved in the debate to read his harsh letters to a certain intellectual rival, Zhu Xi fiercely attacked those whose learning he identifies as incorrect, empty, or distractive. His major targets included Lu Jiuyuan (陸九淵, i.e., Lu Xiang Shan 陸象山, 1139-1193 CE), the leader of the "school of mind-heart" (xin xue 心學) who belittled book learning; the hopelessly utilitarian scholars represented by Chen Liang (陳亮 1143-1195 CE) and other statecraft writers from the Wuzhou 婺州 region (modern Zhejiang province); and the morally corrupt and short-sighted politicians in the court. In his later years, Zhu Xi's suspicion and criticism even extended to his once close ally Lv Zuqian (呂祖謙, 1137-1181 CE) and Lv's brother Lv Zujian (呂祖儉, c.a., 1135 CE), claiming that the latter had deviated from the correct learning (zhengxue 正學) and become the advocates of Guanzhong 管仲-like utilitarianist and Shangyang 商鞅-like ruthless legalists. In other words, Zhu Xi's main strategy to proselytize and recruit new members was trying to convince people that his learning was the correct learning (Bol, 2022, Ch. 2).

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

— Yes

Notes: Neo-Confucianism as an intellectual and social movement is by itself a reformist movement in the long tradition of Confucianism. Its primary goal is to purify and renew the Confucian heritage. Before the Song, especially before Zhu Xi's synthesization and renovation, it had accumulated layers of admixtures including Taoism (ancient and Neo-Taoism), Legalism, and various concepts that were associated with the Buddhist religion in one way or another. Although the core of Confucianism as a teaching and an ideology had remained basically the same since it was adopted as the state orthodoxy in the second century BCE, it was not as pure as the Song thinkers believed it was supposed to be, and thus their resolution to purify and revitalize the heritage from within. - One of the most distinctive characteristics of Neo-Confucianism as a reformist movement is the ascendancy of the four groups of texts that constitute the Four Books, a new canon of the renewed tradition. The Analects, which collects Confucius' own words and his disciples' remarks about the Master's life and deeds, had always been considered essential in rudimentary education, but it never made it into the Classics (jing 經). Some scholars believe the "Seven Classics" in the Eastern Han includes the Analects, but others doubt whether the phrase refers to Confucian texts. They believe it refers more likely to a group of Daoist or Buddhist scripts. The Mencius used to be merely one of the pre-Qin "masters' books" (zishu 子書) but had been assigned increasing significance since the mid-Tang. Leading Confucian scholars of various generations prior to Zhu Xi, including Han Yu 韓愈 (768-824 CE), Ouyang Xiu 歐陽脩 (1007-1072 CE), Wang Anshi 王安石 (1021-1086 CE), and the Cheng brothers - Cheng Hao 程顥 (1032-1085 CE) and Cheng Yi 程頤 (1033-1107 CE) - had already noticed the hermeneutic potentials in Mencius' teaching. Han Yu

and Li Ao 李翱 (774–836 CE) are among the first scholars who paid special attention to the Great Learning and the Doctrine of Mean, which are two chapters selected from the Book of Rites (Liji, 禮記). Han and Li's discussions laid the foundation for the Cheng brothers and Zhu Xi to further expound. But it was in Zhu Xi's hands that the four groups of texts were first combined together, prioritized in the Confucian teaching, given systematic and coherent interpretations, and finally became the Four Books—the new textbook of Confucianian teaching that would surpass the Five Classics to become the foundation of state orthodoxy.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

— No

Is there material significance to the text?

— No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

— No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

— Yes

Notes: The four groups of the original texts that constitute the Four Books—the Great Learning, the Doctrine of Mean, the Analects, the Mencius— had remained the same themselves when Zhu Xi first combined them together and interpreted it as one learning compendium in the twelfth century. But the “collected commentaries” (jizhu 集注) and the exegetical layer that are attached to this new canon had evolved through different stages of Zhu Xi's scholarly career with multiple editions; some of them survived to date. In 1177 CE, Zhu Xi finished the first draft of the collected commentaries of the four books and a separate work titled The Tentative Inquiries into the Four Books (Sishu huowen 四書或問), setting the general framework for this monumental scholarship. The former was first printed with the title The Collected Commentaries of the Chapters and Verses of the Four Books (Sishu zhangju jizhu 四書章句集注) in 1182 CE at Wuzhou 婺州 (in modern Zhejiang province). This was the first time the term “sishu” appeared in the publishing world. Japanese scholar Tsuchida Kenjiro scrutinized all of Zhu Xi's editorial works on the sishu (see below for the full list) and proposed the sequence Zhu Xi worked on them based on the content of each work. Tsuchida suggested that before Huowen and Jizhu, Zhu Xi actually had two other sishu manuscripts: Jingyi (The Essential Meanings [of the Four Books] 精義) and Jilve (The Editorial Basics [on the Four Books] 輯略). Huowen is in fact a work of investigation into the inconsistent or contradictory interpretations regarding the same line, chapter, or theme collected in Jingyi and Jilve. Jizhu was done either after Huowen or concurrent with it. And according to Tsuchida, Huowen best presents Zhu Xi's early effort in synthesizing Daoxue's (the Learning of the Way, 道學, exchangeable with the term “Lixue” the Learning of the Principle 理學, but refers particularly to the early stage of Lixue) orthodoxy interpretations of the four groups of texts at issue. The revised second edition of SSZJJZ was printed in 1192 CE. It was prohibited a few years later due to Zhu Xi and his patron's failure in political struggle and the government's identifying of his teaching and writing as “false learning” (weixue 偽學). Zhu Xi did not stop revising SSZJJZ until the very last moment of his life. Almost

blind, he dictated the changes to his disciples. Modern scholars' studies show that there are at least 15 different kinds of editorial and commentary works generated out of the master's decades of study on the Four Books, with only four of them surviving or partially surviving to date. The list includes: 新定大學 (lost), 新定中庸 (lost), 四書章句集注, 四書或問, 論孟精義, 大學集解 (lost), 論語集解 (lost), 論語訓蒙口義 (lost), 孟子集解 (lost), 孟子要略 (lost), 中庸詳說 (lost), 中庸輯略 (partially survived), 四書音訓 (lost), and 四書集義 (lost).

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

Notes: Zhu Xi revised SSZJJZ multiple times throughout his life, with the last edition being the most comprehensive one that best presents his agenda.

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Yes. SSZJJZ is a work of what's called the Neo-Confucian hermeneutics. It contains two major parts: four groups of original texts Zhu Xi selected from the inherited Confucian Classics or ancient Confucian canons, and its exegetical layer which includes Zhu Xi's own glossaries, interpretations, and comments he collected and edited from earlier scholarship.

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: The Four Books are used for self-cultivation.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: None

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: None

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Notes: - The making of so-called “Cheng-Zhu school of the Learning of the Principle” (Cheng-Zhu lixue 程朱理學), the most noticeable school in the broad lixue (the Learning of the Principle, in most cases exchangeable with the term Neo-Confucianism) movement, is a complex historical phenomenon and result of an interplay of multiple forces. But Zhu Xi’s SSZJJZ as a new Confucian canon is perhaps the most decisive factor that raised this intellectual lineage to the privileged status it enjoyed in Yuan, Ming and Qing China. Zhu Xi’s appreciation of the Cheng brothers’ learning and his endeavor to lift them as his pioneers to “revitalize” the Confucian heritage is ubiquitous in his writings and deeds. But such appreciation and endeavor could hardly be better presented anywhere else than SSZJJZ. According to Shen Shuhua 申淑華’s most recent study (Shen, 2019), half of Zhu Xi’s “collected commentaries” come from the Cheng brothers and their followers’ works. Citations of Cheng Hao and Cheng Yi are up to 311, Yin Tun (尹焞 1068-1131 CE) up to 102, Yang Shi (楊時 1053-1135 CE) to 77, Xie Liangzuo (謝良佐) up to 51, Lv Da lin (呂大臨) up to 17, You Zuo (游酢) up to 8. Shen then concludes that SSZJJZ is basically a collection of the Cheng school’s remarks, with Zhu Xi being the one to decide whose and which remarks could make it into the Confucian orthodox and the Chinese elites’ structure of knowledge for centuries to come.

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Intellectual Elect

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Notes: Zhu Xi understands spirit-mind— or “mind-heart” (xin 心) as it is more commonly used in sinological scholarship on Chinese philosophy— as what “governs” (zai 宰) how one feels and behaves and whether those feelings and behaviors are proper or moderate (zhong jie 中節). In its relationship with the physical body (shen 身), which in itself is one of the objects (wu 物) in the phenomenal world, the mind-heart rules (zhu 主) the body; it is “the subject rather than the object” (wei zhu er bu wei ke zhe 為主而不為客者) and “the dominator rather than the dominated” (ming wu er bu ming yu wu zhe 命物而不命於物者). With regard to its substance (benti 本體), mind-heart is equivalent to the three ultimate concepts in Zhu Xi’s theory of the Way, which are “one” themselves: Moral Nature of man and things (xing 性), Coherence/ Pattern/ Principle (li 理), and humanity (ren 仁). Zhu Xi articulates that “The mind-heart is the principle. When manifested in mind-heart, it’s called human nature. When manifested in things and events, it’s called principle.” (Xing ji li ye. Zai xin huanzuo xing, zai shi huanzuo li. 性即理也。在心喚做性，在事喚作理。) Despite the fundamental irreconcilability between Zhu Xi and his primary intellectual rival and leader of the “school of mind” (xin xue 心學) Lu Jiuyuan 陸九淵 about the necessity and methodology of making meticulous efforts (ximi gongfu 細密工夫) to keep one’s mind untarnished, both Zhu and Lu inherited Mencius’ faith in humans’ innate goodness, and both cited Mencius heavily in their writings or remarks. However, this does not mean xin (mind-heart) is unconditionally equivalent to li (Principle 理) or ren (humanity 仁). Zhu Xi articulates that the sages use mind-heart to indicate (zhishi 指示) the preservation of humanity, but humanity is not necessarily the modifier (xingrong 形容) of the mind-heart. The accordance of human mind (renxin 人心) with the moral mind (daoxin 道心) is a perfect state to be achieved through constant and conscious effort. This is also where Zhu Xi and Lu Jiuyuan diverge in understanding mind-heart. For the latter, there is no distinction between the principle of heaven (tianli 天理) and human desire (renyu 人欲); the principle and all things that manifest this principle are “already complete in oneself” (jie bei yu wo, 皆備於我, Mencius 7A.4); and there is no distinction between each individual’s mind-heart with that of the sages of all times and all places. Therefore, all one needs to do is to “take self-examination” (fan er si zhi 反而思之, or, qieji zi ran 切己自反) and to “correct one’s mistakes and reform to do good” (gai guo qian shan 改過遷善). But Lu Jiuyuan stops here and provides no specific instructions for self-examination and self-correcting. What’s more, with Zhu Xi constantly in his mind as a major debater over this issue, Lu Jiuyuan explicitly comments on the futility of investigating objects (gewu 格物) and the vainness of book learning, the two major methods Zhu Xi proposes for cultivating/ nourishing (yang 養), rectifying (zheng 正), and preserving (cun 存) one’s mind in order to maintain its humane nature. Lu Jiuyuan asserts that one is not— as Zhu Xi promises— able to extract the

principle by investigating all things and events (gewu qiongli 格物窮理) as these are infinite, and to lift the burden is in itself a form of gewu. Lu also believes that reading and learning only burdens one in their recovery of the original mind, which is innately good and unobstructed. It is in this context that he utters one of his most astonishing statements that “All the Six Classics are one’s footnotes” (liujing jie wo zhujiao 六經皆我注腳), if one knows the fundamentals. Lu Jiuyuan’s approaches have been characterized as “honoring the moral nature” (zun dexing 尊德性), as opposed to that of Zhu Xi: “following the path of inquiry and study” (dao wenxue 道問學).

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– No

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Yes

Notes: Two pairs of notions that appear the most frequently are “active (dong 動) versus tranquil (jing 靜)” and “before (wei fa 未發) or after (yi fa 已發) [feelings] are aroused”. A similar pair to the latter is “the state of non-being (wei xing 未形) and the state of being (ke jian 可見)”. Because the mind-heart is essentially an active thing (dong wu 動物), it involves both states of tranquility and activity. Once active, the mind is subject to the influence of material force and various sorts of feelings and desires. This explains the reconcilability of the two seemingly contradictory statements made by Zhu Xi: that the human mind and moral mind are one, and that human mind can be immoral. This is what Zhang Zai (張載, 1020-1077 CE) calls “the mind commands man’s nature and feelings” (xin tong xing qing 心統性情), a quotation Zhu Xi highly acclaims and cites often.

↳ Are there generally positive or negative associations with aggregates?

– Generally positive

Notes: The state of “tranquility” / “before [feelings] are aroused” / “non-being” is considered positive, because it’s the original and innate state of the moral mind. The state of “action” / “after [feelings] are aroused” / “being” is not negative per se, but needs to be monitored and directed.

↳ If associations with mental aggregates are neither positive or negative, are there other important details to know?

– Specify: No

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

Notes: What concerns Zhu Xi and his learning community more is not the mind-body dualism but the difficulty in understanding and coping with the paradoxes of the human mind’s innate moral substance (ti 體) and its tendency to become immoral in operation (yong 用). In other words, what’s usually paired with (the innately good) “mind-heart” in the Neo-Confucian discourse is not “body” but notions that are considered to be the trigger of such tendency or factors that are associated with partiality and diversion, such as “material force”, “feeling” and “desire”.

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– Yes

Notes: As explained in the answer to the previous question, what concerns Zhu Xi and his learning community more is not the mind-body dualism but the difficulty in understanding and coping with the paradoxes of the human mind's innate moral substance (ti 體) and its tendency to become immoral in operation (yong 用). In other words, what's usually paired with (the innately good) "mind-heart" in the Neo-Confucian discourse is not "body" but notions that are considered to be the trigger of such tendency or factors that are associated with partiality and diversion, such as "material force", "feeling" and "desire". In the voluminous *A Collection of Conversations of Master Zhu* (Zhu zi yulei 朱子語類), ti-yong (substance/nature-operation/function 體用) of the human mind is among the most discussed (if not debated) topics. In his *A Treatise on the Examination of the Mind* (guan xin shuo 觀心說), after claiming in the opening passage that the mind "rules the body" (zhu hu shen zhe 主乎身者), Zhu Xi quickly shifts his focus to the instructions of nourishing the moral nature of the mind and distinguishing the Confucian sages' understanding of human mind from that of the Buddhists, whose doctrines are condemned and cautioned against by Zhu as "precarious and oppressive" (wei er po 危而迫), "dangerous and obstructed" (xian er se 險而塞).

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– No

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Notes: Except for a few passages from the Analects and Mencius mentioning the general moral principles of funerals, such as the period of mourning. Both Confucius and Mencius advocate three years of mourning for parents and the Son of Heaven. See, for example, Analects 17.21 and Mencius 5a.2.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Notes: The most well-known Analects quotations about supernatural beings and powers include the following two lines: “He sacrificed to the spirits, as if the spirits were present.” (3.12), and “The subjects on which the Master did not talk were: extraordinary things, feats of strength, disorder, and spiritual beings” (7.21). Both avoid articulating the affirmation or negation of the presence of supernatural beings, while remaining focused on the concrete and practical issues in the secular world. Although in some Warring States texts taiji (the Supreme Ultimate 太極) is presented as god, it is rendered in more naturalistic terms in Zhu Xi’s writing. For Zhu Xi, taiji in most contexts is exchangeable with li (Principle 理). It has neither spatial restriction (wu fangsuo 無方所) nor physical form or body (xingti 形體); it existed even before the universe came into being and is manifested in every single part of the phenomenal world. The latter point is often summarized as “Principle is one but its manifestation are many” (li yi fen shu 理一分殊). Modern Chinese philosophers including Fung Yu-lan (馮友蘭 1895–1990 CE) and Carsun Chang (張君勱 1887–1969 CE) have tried to compare taiji with similar notions in Western philosophy. Fung Yu-lan believes that taiji is analogous to what Plato called the Idea of the Good or what Aristotle called God. Carsun Chang did a more detailed comparison between Zhu Xi and Aristotle and concluded that Zhu Xi is an Aristotelian in the field of nature, but closer to Plato when it comes to morality-related issues. Neo-Confucians believe that the dao (the Way 道), the ultimate truth and moving cause of the universe, is the highest goodness, and it is eternal and universal. But dao is not a personified being. Dao in the ontological sense is exchangeable with a few other Neo-Confucian notions including li (the Principle 理), taiji (the Supreme Ultimate 太極), xing (nature of man and things 性), xin (human mind 心, here refers to daoxin 道心, the moral mind), etc. Dao in its substance (ti 體) is unquestionably good, but its various forms of manifestation or operation (yong 用) can be corrupt. Dao is eternal and universal. It is “one” as the ultimate truth but has many manifestations.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Humans and cultural heroes/sages.

Notes: The most discussed deceased cultural hero in the context of Neo-Confucianism is Confucius and the ideal of sagehood that he represents. Confucius himself talks more about the characters of a worthy man (junzi, 君子), but rarely addresses sagehood directly. Mencius is the one who advocates the achievability of sagehood for everyone, an idea that found its strong resonance among the Neo-Confucian thinkers in the 11th and 12th centuries. Zhou Dunyi (1017-1073 CE) responds to the query of “whether sagehood is something one can learn to achieve” (sheng ke xue hu 聖可學乎) and proposes that being sincere (cheng 誠) is the crucial means to “learn to” become a sage. Zhu Xi further develops a full-fledged scheme of how to realize this ideal based on the “eight endeavors” (bamu, 八目) raised in The Great Learning, one of the Four Books: to investigate objects (gewu 格物), then to obtain knowledge (zhizhi, 致知), then to make one’s intention sincere (chengyi, 誠意), then to correct one’s mind (zhengxin, 正心), then to practice self-cultivation (xiushen, 修身), then to manage the family (qijia, 齊家), then to rule the nation (zhiguo, 治國), then to bring order to the world (ping tianxia, 平天下).

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Because there was a gap of over a thousand years between the time when the four groups of texts were first created or written down and the time when they were compiled and edited into the Four Books as the Neo-Confucian canon, any specific social norms mentioned in the original texts would hardly be applicable to the context of the 12th century. However, the general moral principles justifying those proper social norms are believed to be timeless and universal. Through his selection of earlier scholars' commentaries on the original texts and his own elaborated or revised interpretations, Zhu Xi advises his readers on a wide range of issues regarding social norms including individual behavior, character cultivation, family governing, promotion of cohesion in kinship lineage groups, building of community covenant, ritual practices, etc. With Zhu Xi, the Way is by no means empty speculation and is "not distant from human beings" (dao bu yuan ren 道不遠人). It is, and should be, manifested in the various life situations and social norms.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

Notes: Moral cultivation is indeed assigned the utmost importance in Zhu Xi's learning and is reckoned by the master as one's ultimate pursuit. But Zhu Xi's prioritization of morality has been understated by many because of his stress on "dao wenxue" (following the path of inquiry and study 道問學), a notion that is often paired with—and contrasted to—"zun dexing" (honoring the moral nature 尊德性). The latter characterizes the learning of Lu Jiuyuan, Zhu Xi's major intellectual rival and the leading philosopher of the "school of mind-heart" of the time. The truth is, Zhu Xi never intends to set the two approaches against each other, and he never discards either of them. For Zhu Xi, "honoring the moral nature" exists as a presumption and provides a general framework for the work of "inquiry and study" to be carried out meaningfully. Zhu Xi does assign an essential role to knowledge and writes intensively on it, but intellectual pursuit is still paradoxically secondary in his system because it is the operative part of the system rather than the ultimate purpose it serves. In other words, knowledge—both book knowledge and knowledge obtained from investigating objects—should always be morality oriented. Zhu Xi never advocates for knowledge's own sake and without a moral focus. It is also for this reason that Zhu Xi creatively prioritizes the Four Books over the Five Classics and other texts such as history works and various forms of literary writings, making it the first and foremost curriculum in his general educational program. He believes that the Four Books are pedagogically more efficient in cultivating and perfecting students' moral nature. Works like Analects and Mencius take less time to comprehend but yield more results. The same reason also explains why Zhu Xi put the Five Classics before historical works in his teaching. He claims that the representation of moral principles in history is mediated by the change of the past and present, and thus relatively irrelevant regarding self-cultivation. As for literature, although Zhu Xi no longer repeats Cheng Yi's notoriously famous slogan "Crafting literature harms the Way" (zuo wen hai dao 作文害道) as an avid poet himself, and also reckons that arts are entitled to their own right of existence as a separate realm coexisting with that of morality and knowledge, he cautions students against self-indulging in literary writing because it distracts them

from the more serious and proper commitment: the pursuit of moral perfection. According to Zhu Xi's disciple Yang Ji 楊楫, the master only discussed literature and arts with students "in his spare time." In short, Zhu Xi's conception of broad human culture is both pluralistic and hierarchical. Moral cultivation and other conventional pursuits all have their separate realms, but all of them are held together under the Way with the highest one reserved for morality.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Strongly present & highlighted

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: No, most moral norms prescribed in the Four Books are general moral norms, applicable (or even supposedly universal) to broad historical contexts.

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– All individuals (any time period)

Notes: In theory, moral cultivation is for everyone to practice, but literati— mainly the male and educated— are those who have the chance to exemplify all the moral principles in sangang (Three Bonds, 三綱) and wulun (Five Moral Relationships 五倫), the fundamental relationships in a Confucian society. The Three Bonds refers to the relationship between father and son, lord and retainer, and husband and wife. The Five Moral Relationships adds two more to the Three bonds: the relationship between teacher and student, and between elder (brother) and younger (brother).

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: One of the most advocated virtues in Zhu Xi's teaching based on the Four Books is jing (reverence, seriousness, attentiveness, alertness 敬). Zhu Xi inherits Cheng Yi's formula that "Self-cultivation requires seriousness; the pursuit of learning depends on the extension of knowledge" (Han yang xu yong jing, jin xue zai zhizhi. 涵養須用敬, 進學在致知) and places it at the very center of his teaching throughout his long intellectual life. Although many scholars distinguish Zhu Xi and Lu Jiuyuan by characterizing their respective approach as "dao wenxue" (following the path of inquiry and study 道問學) and "zun dexing" (honoring the moral nature 尊德性), Zhu Xi actually never advocates book learning for its own sake. He believes that learning— both book learning and learning through investigating objects— should always be morally oriented. Therefore he sees Cheng Yi's formula as a more satisfactory reformulation of the polarity of "zun dexing" and "dao wenxue", which unifies the two approaches with jing. For Zhu Xi, to exercise seriousness (yong jing 用敬) is not only required in book learning, such an attitude should be adopted at anytime anywhere and in everything one does. The notion of jing has wide connotations. Depending on the context, it can mean being awed and cautious (wei jin 畏謹) and avoiding self-indulging (fangsi 放肆); or keeping one's mind simultaneously in ease (xian 閑) and focused (zhu 主); or staying alert and aware (xingxing 惺惺); or always being ready for self-examination and rectification (jiandian 檢點). As many have observed, one of Zhu Xi's most monumental contributions to Neo-Confucian learning is his emphasis and design of the methodologies in achieving the lofty goals. His discussions on jing presents a good example of this. Because jing is both an ideal psychological state in which one's human mind (renxin 人心) and moral mind (daoxin 道心) become "one" and a specific training that one takes to achieve that ideal

psychological state, Zhu Xi has introduced various practices for the training of the fallible and constantly active human mind. Among these practices reading is particularly helpful because one's mind is always on alert when reading. Reading prevents people from indulging their minds in empty speculation and having their moral nature lapse into laxity.

- ↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity
– Yes
- ↳ Courage (in battle)
– Yes
- ↳ Courage (generic)
– Yes
- ↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
– Yes
- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
– Yes
- ↳ Generosity/charity
– Yes
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
– Yes
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
– Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
– No
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
– Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
– Yes

- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
 - Notes: Not always stressed.
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
 - Notes: Not particularly stressed.
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - Yes
 - Notes: As long as it is attained through righteous means.
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

Notes: Physical attractiveness, especially when it's in the erotic sense, is cautioned against. But modest and elegant demeanor is encouraged.

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– No

Notes: The virtues mentioned in earlier questions already constitute a comprehensive list of Neo-Confucian virtues.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: The Confucian teaching strongly stresses filial piety and that one needs to take three years of mourning at their parent(s)' death. Although there are no precise instructions regarding the constraints on sexual activity, one is not allowed to marry and not supposed to have newborns during this mourning window.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer,

etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: A school of thinking.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– An empire

Notes: From the third year in the Qingyuan reign (1197 CE) to the second year of the Jiatai reign (1202 CE), Zhu Xi's learning was condemned by the court as "false learning" (weixue 偽學). The court was by then under the control of the political rivals of Zhu Xi's patron. As a result, all of Zhu Xi's works including his most updated version of SSZJJZ, along with fifty-eight other scholars' works, were banned nation-wide for several years. This event is known as the "Proscription of Qingyuan". (qingyuan dangjin 慶元黨禁)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1197 CE - 1202 CE

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: As the founder of the study of the Four Books, Zhu Xi taught his SSZJJZ and other Neo-Confucian works on a regular basis in three of his own private academies: Cold Spring Study (Hanquan jingshe 寒泉精舍, built in 1170 CE in Jianyang, Fujian); Wuyi Study (Wuyi jingshe, 武夷精舍, built in 1183 CE in Wuyi mountain); and Bamboo Grove Study (Zhulin jingshe, 竹林精舍, built in 1194 CE in Jianyang, Fujian, later renamed as Cangzhou jingshe 滄州精舍). Jingshe is a special term Zhu Xi and a few other Neo-Confucian scholars including Lu Jiuyuan adopted to name the private academies (shuyuan 書院) that were exclusively dedicated to (Neo-)Confucian education. Shuyuan as an educational institution – and in many cases residential space – for young students first appeared in the Northern Song. There

were both public and private academies in the Northern Song. Although private shuyuan became the majority in the Southern Song, public academies still existed. Many of them were revived from the old Northern Song official academies in localities, where low-ranking officials served as instructors to hold public sessions from time to time for the local learning community. Despite the common problem of bureaucratic laxity, these public academies did offer their students various benefits: boarding, stipends, and other privileges such as quasi-official status, tax and labor service exemptions. The primary function of private academies in Zhu Xi's time was "discoursing on learning" (jiangxue 講學). Scholars of renown would be invited to teach at these academies either as lecturers-in-residence or visiting lectures. They were free to develop their own curriculum and were not required to be aligned with what was taught in the official school system. Zhu Xi, for example, always positioned the Four Books, especially the "yumeng" (Analects and the Mencius 語孟) part, at the center of his teaching. The teaching was not confined to formal sessions either. Some shuyuan owners who invited known scholars from outside were known scholars themselves: Zhu Xi is one of them. Another famous example is Zhu Xi's life-long friend and peer, historian Lv Zuqian 呂祖謙 (1137- 1181 CE), the de facto initiator of the famous Lize shuyuan 麗澤書院. But many more shuyuan were founded and operated by wealthy local families that had the needs, will and capacity to build schools for their own sons and male descendants for multiple generations to come. In addition to discoursing on learning, private academies of this time also functioned as libraries, shrines, and sometimes publishing houses. Thanks to the support of the academic community and wealthy families, private academies often had the best edition of Confucian classics and scholarship. Many shuyuan also practiced worship ceremonies or sacrifice rituals for Confucius. Zhu Xi was one of the ardent practitioners of this jikong (sacrificing Confucius 祭孔) tradition, claiming it to be a visible and reverent gesture to acknowledge the unsurpassable contribution Confucius did for education. Later private shuyuan carried on this legacy, but the worshiped one sometimes became Master Zhu himself or other Neo-Confucian masters they particularly identified with. Zhu Xi saw private academies as a critical means and venue to promote the Neo-Confucian movement. There were as many as twenty-four private academies that Zhu Xi had served or was affiliated with in various forms throughout his life. And it was in his Cold Spring Study that he and Lv Zuqian co-edited *Reflections on Things at Hand* (Jinsi lu 近思錄), another Neo-Confucian canon. When he was assigned to Nankang county 南康軍 (in modern Jiangxi) in the late 1170s and early 1181s, Zhu Xi took the chance to rebuild and revive its famed White Deer Grotto Academy (Bailu dong shuyuan 白鹿洞書院). It was said that Zhu Xi once recruited into the academy two dozen new degree holder of the civil examination who were in the midst of waiting for the court's position assigning, encouraging them to take advantage of the academy's serene environment to distant themselves from the rootless learning of "mere recitation"-- an innuendo regard the learning of examination (keju zhi xue 科舉之學) that he disparaged - and redirect their focus on the "correct learning" (zhengxue 正學). In fact, Zhu Xi's adoption of the name of jingshe is in itself an intended effort to combat heretical teachings. Jingshe was known to many by then (and perhaps even so to date) as the translation of vihara, a Buddhist term referring to monasteries or dwelling of renunciation. But according to Zhu Xi, the word jingshe was originally from Guanzi 管子 and referred to the lecturing and discussing venues for Confucian scholars during the Warring States period; and jing means, ironically, "to purify". It was the Buddhists that later took the term for themselves and imbued it with foreign meanings, not the other way around. Another leading Neo-Confucian scholar Lu Jiuyuan, Zhu Xi's academic rival and his major debater at the Goose Lake Meeting, shared the same intention with Zhu in this regard.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

— Yes

Notes: As the founder of the study of the Four Books, Zhu Xi taught his SSZJJZ and other Neo-Confucian works on a regular basis in three of his own private academies: Cold Spring Study (Hanquan jingshe 寒泉精舍, built in 1170 CE in Jianyang, Fujian); Wuyi Study (Wuyi jingshe, 武夷精舍, built in 1183 CE in Wuyi mountain); and Bamboo Grove Study (Zhulin jingshen, 竹林精舍, built in 1194 CE in Jianyang,

Fujian, later renamed as Cangzhou jingshe 滄州精舍). Jingshe is a special term Zhu Xi and a few other Neo-Confucian scholars including Lu Jiuyuan adopted to name the private academies (shuyuan 書院) that were exclusively dedicated to (Neo-)Confucian education. Shuyuan as an educational institution – and in many cases residential space – for young students first appeared in the Northern Song. There were both public and private academies in the Northern Song. Although private shuyuan became the majority in the Southern Song, public academies still existed. Many of them were revived from the old Northern Song official academies in localities, where low-ranking officials served as instructors to hold public sessions from time to time for the local learning community. Despite the common problem of bureaucratic laxity, these public academies did offer their students various benefits: boarding, stipends, and other privileges such as quasi-official status, tax and labor service exemptions. The primary function of private academies in Zhu Xi's time was "discoursing on learning" (jiangxue 講學). Scholars of renown would be invited to teach at these academies either as lecturers-in-residence or visiting lectures. They were free to develop their own curriculum and were not required to be aligned with what was taught in the official school system. Zhu Xi, for example, always positioned the Four Books, especially the "yumeng" (Analects and the Mencius 語孟) part, at the center of his teaching. The teaching was not confined to formal sessions either. Some shuyuan owners who invited known scholars from outside were known scholars themselves: Zhu Xi is one of them. Another famous example is Zhu Xi's life-long friend and peer, historian Lv Zuqian 呂祖謙 (1137–1181 CE), the de facto initiator of the famous Lize shuyuan 麗澤書院. But many more shuyuan were founded and operated by wealthy local families that had the needs, will and capacity to build schools for their own sons and male descendants for multiple generations to come. In addition to discoursing on learning, private academies of this time also functioned as libraries, shrines, and sometimes publishing houses. Thanks to the support of the academic community and wealthy families, private academies often had the best edition of Confucian classics and scholarship. Many shuyuan also practiced worship ceremonies or sacrifice rituals for Confucius. Zhu Xi was one of the ardent practitioners of this jikong (sacrificing Confucius 祭孔) tradition, claiming it to be a visible and reverent gesture to acknowledge the unsurpassable contribution Confucius did for education. Later private shuyuan carried on this legacy, but the worshiped one sometimes became Master Zhu himself or other Neo-Confucian masters they particularly identified with. Zhu Xi saw private academies as a critical means and venue to promote the Neo-Confucian movement. There were as many as twenty-four private academies that Zhu Xi had served or was affiliated with in various forms throughout his life. And it was in his Cold Spring Study that he and Lv Zuqian co-edited *Reflections on Things at Hand* (Jinsi lu 近思錄), another Neo-Confucian canon. When he was assigned to Nankang county 南康軍 (in modern Jiangxi) in the late 1170s and early 1181s, Zhu Xi took the chance to rebuild and revive its famed White Deer Grotto Academy (Bailu dong shuyuan 白鹿洞書院). It was said that Zhu Xi once recruited into the academy two dozen new degree holder of the civil examination who were in the midst of waiting for the court's position assigning, encouraging them to take advantage of the academy's serene environment to distance themselves from the rootless learning of "mere recitation" – an innuendo regard the learning of examination (keju zhi xue 科舉之學) that he disparaged – and redirect their focus on the "correct learning" (zhengxue 正學). In fact, Zhu Xi's adoption of the name of jingshe is in itself an intended effort to combat heretical teachings. Jingshe was known to many by then (and perhaps even so to date) as the translation of vihara, a Buddhist term referring to monasteries or dwelling of renunciation. But according to Zhu Xi, the word jingshe was originally from Guanzi 管子 and referred to the lecturing and discussing venues for Confucian scholars during the Warring States period; and jing means, ironically, "to purify". It was the Buddhists that later took the term for themselves and imbued it with foreign meanings, not the other way around. Another leading Neo-Confucian scholar Lu Jiuyuan, Zhu Xi's academic rival and his major debater at the Goose Lake Meeting, shared the same intention with Zhu in this regard.

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Notes: It does not provide education irrelevant to Neo-Confucian doctrines.

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Notes: The Yuan court's 1313 decree recovered civil examinations that had been suspended for a few decades after the establishment of the Mongol regime. The decree also assigned Zhu Xi's SSZJJZ as the exclusive curriculum for the examination, making it the most read text among those who aimed to gain keju degrees. Participation in the civil examination system (keju 科舉) alone— even without succeeding in it and getting a degree— was enough to provide one with various benefits, including access to local officials, freedom from labor service for registered students, and connections to other elite families of similar status, and etc. These preferential policies were implemented for several centuries till the termination of keju in 1919 CE.

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: There are a few places in the Analects mentioning war or military affairs. Confucius in general is considered anti-war; he cautions against it and refuses to advise warlord who consults him about waging war (e.g., Analects 7.13, 15.1). Mencius is known for his support of “righteous war” (yizhan 義戰), which he defines as wars waged by the Son of the Heaven (with the endowed heavenly mandate) against unrighteous warlords who are under the rule of the Son of the Heaven. (Mencius 14.48b). So according to Mencius, there were no yizhan in the Spring and Autumn period, for none of the wars was done by supreme authority to punish its subjects by force of arms. And wars between hostile states are not qualified to be called zheng 征, which Zhu Xi explained as zheng 正, to correct.

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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